

DO WOMEN MATTER IN SOUTH AFRICAN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION?

Perceptions From Impendle Local Municipality

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Abstract: The study seeks to examine whether women matter in the South African Public and drawing perceptions from iMpendle Local Municipality. The democratic dispensation has put gender equality as one of key goals of public service, however after 30 years of democracy in public administration and local government. iMpendle Local Municipality continues to suffer strides of inequality of men and women in local government, owing to the patriarchy as a social construct including local government. The study aims to analyse perceptions of women on the mechanism used by public administration to promote equal access in local government, and, to recommend effective strategies for public administration to accelerate gender equality in local government. The study used qualitative methodology in which structured interviews were used to collect data from the municipal officials. A total of 30 participants were purposively identified and clustered for data collection, and 27 were available for interviews. In terms of data analysis, a mixture of content and thematic analyses was used. A Liberal Feminist Theory is adopted as a lens to underpin the analysis of how mechanisms to accelerate gender equality. The study concludes that women are predominantly in the periphery, and remain excluded, and with limited effort on the part of public administration and local government to accelerate gender equality. The recommends that public administration and local government to disrupts and abolish laws that discriminating based on gender, through introduction of implementation strategies, monitoring and evaluation of policies, and programs to include women and accelerate gender equality.

INTRODUCTION

The debate about gender equality has been broadly debated in a broader academic discipline. This is a global debate which has seen most organisations being at loggerheads about the implementation of various policies, legislations, and programs to promote gender equality in South Africa. According to Horowitz, (2023) in 1994, at the new dawn of democracy, the life and lived

realities of black women of South Africa, democracy was seen as the inception of promising gender regulations and policy frameworks for justice and fairness to all. The first step of the South African government was to formulate the legislative and policy framework that promotes gender equality and women empowerment in all sectors of society, (Fourie, 2024).

South Africans are emerging out of an era of institutional racism; one in which a person's worth has been dictated by the colour of their skin. This translates into a reality where the lighter the shade of colour, the greater the value; the darker the hue, the less the value of the individual. Alongside institutional racism has been the issue of gender discrimination. While women in general have been negatively affected by racism, African women have carried a disproportionate burden of the under-development caused by relegation to periphery by a system that favours men.

Nchofoung, et al (2023) states that gender equality has always been a core value of the struggle for a democratic South Africa. This value was immediately adopted into the country's governance processes with the establishment of the new dispensation in 1994 and has been enshrined in the 1996 Constitution of South Africa. It is the strong political commitment to this value that has moved the South African government to craft gender sensitive national priorities. The commitment to achieving gender equality has motivated South Africa to accede to regional and international instruments promoting gender equality; increased awareness of gender issues in all spheres of life; enhanced the integration of gender considerations into government policies and programmes. According to Eisenstein, (2023) the commitment to gender equality has historically been supported by the majority of South Africans committed to equality and to a democratic and non-racist society. Supporters of this principle include members of political parties, the women's movement, religious community, NGOs and the youth movement.

After a long struggle against an oppressive system of government, characterised by institutional racism, patriarchy and oppression, a new democracy was ushered in on 27 April 1994 with the mandate of advancing the country towards a democratic, non-racist, non-sexist society. Through the 1996 Constitution, the people of South Africa committed themselves to, among others, the values of "human dignity, the achievement of equality and advancement of human rights and freedoms" (Constitution of 1996). Non-racism and non-sexism form the cornerstone of South Africa's transformation project, which is well underway. The government's objectives are to de-racialise and engender all institutions of the state and of civil society.

A successful public governance implements policies which are derived from the public participation. This happens where both genders in the public are given a platform to express the challenges they are facing. Public institutions have been putting emphasis in the women empowerment as a key factor to address factors that impede on the successful public governance. However, in the 30th year of democratic state, there challenge of women empowerment continues to haunt public governance owing to lack of disrupting systems like

patriarchy, monitoring and evaluation, and inclusion of women to be part of women empowerment policy implementation. The objectives of this article are:

- To analyse perceptions of women on the mechanism used by public administration to promote equal access in local government, and,
- To recommend effective strategies for public administration to accelerate gender equality in local government.

To achieve this, the article begins by providing a location of the study, then systematically review gender equality from the perspective of South African Public Administration, and Local Government in general and iMpendle Local Municipality in particular. Following this, a methodology and a conceptual framework is explored to guide the findings and recommendation.

THE MUNICIPAL PROFILE AND WOMEN REPRESENTATION

iMpendle Local Municipality is one of the smallest Municipalities in the Country. In terms of Section 9 of the Municipal Structures Act, 117 of 1998. The iMpendle Local Municipality falls under Category B. Category B Municipalities (Local) share executive and legislative authority with Category C municipalities (District) within whose area they are located (as defined in Section 155 (1) of the Constitution (Act 108 of 1996)

iMpendle Local Municipality is a town in uMgungundlovu District Municipality in the KwaZulu-Natal province of South Africa. iMpendle town is 48 km west of Pietermaritzburg and 37 km north-east of Bulwer. It was founded in 1894 and since 1948 has been administered by a health committee.

The iMpendle Local Municipality is a Category B municipality located within the uMgungundlovu District in KwaZulu-Natal. It is one of seven municipalities in the district. It is situated outside the primary and secondary movement systems of the district and is some distance away from the major tourist and trade routes, although two important roads mark its borders.

iMpendle Local Municipality conducts an annual Take a Girl Child programme that is treated as an annual event. The annual Take a Girl Child to Work initiative samples 20 matrics students from various iMpendle High Schools with the intention to give them chance to experience a working environment. In this programme, the students participate in on-the-job shadowing with all the municipal departments. The learners are informed of career options available within iMpendle Local Municipality.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Women empowerment and gender equality are the part of the South African sustainable development goals that were adopted by the country's government, to bridge the gap between the periphery and the epicentre. The pre-democratic government centralised to a certain group of people, and relegated other people. The problem has been lack of women inclusiveness in

public administration, despite promotion of equality by the same public administrators. This is despite the fact that women make more numbers than men in population, but men has more number is strategic and decision making spaces. This research seeks to establish whether women matter in public administration in general, and specifically in iMpendle Local Municipality.

GENDER EQUALITY: A SOUTH AFRICAN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION PERSPECTIVE

The concept of gender equality in South African public administration, according to Polzer, Nolte, and Seiwald, (2023) means to achieve gender parity within the political sphere, the public and private sectors, clear targets have been put in place in key areas of political and governance levels to promote the advancement, representation and full participation of women in power structures and key decision-making levels. In South Africa, Shafritz, et al (2022) states that gender quality has been a priority for the government and its affiliating institutions, and there is considerable success in advancing women's representation and gender equality across the state machinery. On a similar note, Coe, Wiley, and Bekker, (2019) reveals that while there is a claim of an increase in the implementation of gender equality, there has been a steady increase in the number of women elected as Speakers, Ministers, Deputy Ministers, Premiers, Members of Parliament, Mayors, Councillors, and Chairpersons of Portfolio Committees in the National Parliament.

The government has made bold media statements about gender equality in government. Dalu, and Manyani, (2020) states that while there is slow progress, the acceleration of gender equality and empowerment of women is fundamental to the development and progression of society as a whole. Agarwal, (2018) shares that South Africa has taken significant steps to ensure that gender equality is enshrined in its legislative and policy frameworks. However, this raises concerns about the rate at which the concept of gender equality and women empowerment is still a challenge in South Africa. South Africa is a signatory to several international agreements promoting the empowerment of women and the elimination of discrimination against women (Mckinsey et al (2020). According to Adamma, (2017), gender equality must be adopted from a developmental perspective, meaning that equal participation of women in decision-making structures is crucial for creating gender-sensitive policies and democratic government. This means that if the government and political parties were to implement the policies which advocate for the representation of women in the democratic South African Government, only then would gender equality be realised or almost fully realised in the government spheres (Sanchez-Cruz, Masinire, and Gerónimo-Vázquez, 2020).

Govender, and Vyas-Doorgapersad, (2013) argued that the notion of gender equality and the representation of women should not just be implemented in the executive, legislature and judiciary, but also be monitored in the local spheres of government, and or other community governance

committees. Masango and Mfene (2015) shared that the representation of women and gender equality should be dominant in the African National Congress, the ruling party, by implementing their policy which adopts a quota system for the number of women to be represented on party lists which is currently 50/50 parity. Cold-Ravnkilde (2019) adds that gender equality in public administration should not just be the representation of women in the decision and strategic positions, including the political sphere. Instead, while they occupy those strategic positions, they should be allowed to promote gender equality in the manner they know and understand, without the influence of men, Cornwall, and Rivas, (2015).

According to Parpart, (2019), the post-Apartheid era in South Africa was seen as a critical time for the democratic government to rebuild institutional mechanisms, introduce, and put into effect laws and policies that are consistent with the Constitution in order to usher in a new era of a developing state that included gender equality. Meyer (2014) admitted that 1994 should have been the dawn of the liberation of women. However, two decades into democracy, women are still underrepresented in management positions, with men occupying a significant proportion of decision-making positions in public administration. Furthermore, the same author noted that it is a fact that more women are in senior positions compared to the past, but still, the reality is that women are still underrepresented at the management level of public service. According to Bangani and Vyas-Doorgapersad (2020), the South African Public Service is governed by legal, policy, and regulatory frameworks that call for gender equality in the public sector to provide equal opportunity to male and female employees. However, discrimination against women in the public sector still exists. To promote gender equality in the organisation's strategy and executive responsibilities, work-based policies and programmes, department-based decision-making processes, and public service structures and practices, the government must take remedial action. The concept of gender equality, according to Nkosi and Mulaudzi (2017), is predicated on fairness and equity in politics, society, culture, and the public sector. It is crucial for achieving gender balance.

Every nation's progress depends on achieving gender equality in all spheres of life. As a result, Robinson (2015) suggested that gender equality and concerns about women's empowerment are essential to achieving sustainable development since gender inequality is the most enduring and pervasive global challenge of the 21st century working against its realisation in patriarchal nations. If South African public administration and or public sector desires a growing and improving country, Masango and Mfene (2015) make the case that, among other things, the advancements gained in the pursuit of gender equality should be used to gauge the advancement of democracy in South Africa. According to Moloto, Brink and Nel (2014), the struggle for gender equality in the public sector is a result of gender prejudices, which are views that men and women are better tailored to particular roles based on different qualities and attributes. These generalisations are widespread, often normative as well as

evocative, and they affect all aspects of women's and men's conduct. Singh and Khan (2019) contested the notion of gender stereotypes because it is a system and or a construct that promotes gender inequality, whereas globally, more women than men live in gender inequality. The problem of gender inequality in public service or public administration is addressed by Mannell (2012) who suggested that, among the several obstacles to gender mainstreaming, reluctance to cultural progress is a significant roadblock. Failure to prioritise gender equality and women's viewpoints in decision-making also necessitates re-evaluating priorities and regulations. It involves more than just aiming for equitable access to programmes for men and women.

Mhembwe (2019) observed that because achieving gender equality is a constructive forward-looking strategy for South Africa's growth, it aids in producing substantial and lasting social as well as economic rewards in public administration. According to Nkosi and Mulaudzi (2017), it is critical for women to have equal access to opportunities as males in the government sector and understand that the main responsibility of all the institutions of government is the implementation of gender equality. For gender equality to be achieved, the government must not run away from engaging in a demanding gender mainstreaming strategy.

This idea will lead to what Struckmann, (2018) referred to as equality-centred, which is the foundation of constitutional democracy and an important anti-colonial and anti-patriarchal achievement, but that the malleability of equality indicated that it was always susceptible to various interpretations by the administration and parliament, as well as by judges tasked with implementing the constitution. In light of the requirement to measure Sustainable Development Goals via a gendered lens, the public sector must promote gender responsiveness and gender transformational evaluations, which are currently garnering increased attention, (Gouws, 2017).

In pursuit of gender responsiveness, Bangani, and Vyas-Doorgapersad (2020) argued that the public sector must first acknowledge which is the foundation of the constitutional democracy and an important anti-colonial and anti-patriarchal achievement, but that the malleability of equality indicated that it was always susceptible to various interpretations by the administration and parliament, as well as by judges tasked with implementing the constitution. Nhlapo and Vyas-Doorgapersad (2016) stated that: In government agencies, there is no major or meaningful progress towards gender equality since, other than generic policies and practices that apply to all employees; there are no specific initiatives that acknowledge women as a distinct interest group with unique needs and concerns. Similarly, Msuya (2020) stated that the fight for equality for all people and the elimination of harmful cultural practices that discriminate against women has been going on for a while in the public sector. Libre (2017) added that the notions of gender equality and inequality should be growing concerns in public service because the challenges of gender equality have been evident, in many countries, and in all parts of the world, including South Africa. The president of ANCWL and the then minister in

the Department of Women Affairs in the Presidency, Ms Bathabile Dlamini (2019) was invited on International Women's Day and interviewed by Avantika Seeth, a journalist with the City Press and she said: "There is much work to be done because our nation's structure is based on patriarchy, masculinity, and misogyny. As the minister of women, you can say a lot, but what matters is what you actually do. I'm aware that when our leaders first take office, they all develop a keen awareness of women's issues, but as time goes on, they lose focus on women's issues and neglect the group that is crucial to a vibrant nation. It is an undisputed fact that women face the challenge of discrimination in the public service". Oboh, et al (2021) examined the notion of gender equality in the South African Police Service, and she argued that the power relationships between men and women continue to favour men at the expense of women in policing organisations both nationally and internationally. Furthermore, Nyeck, (2023) concluded that the issue of equality between women and their male counterparts arises in the context of women's struggles in the public service. Carrington, et al (2020) As a result, she recommends that the Ministry of Public Service and Administration works with influential groups like the Commission for Gender Equality, the Department of Women, and the civil society sector to develop a comprehensive strategy to address gender mainstreaming, (Azcona, et al 2020).

GENDER EQUALITY: A SOUTH AFRICAN LOCAL GOVERNMENT PERSPECTIVE

This duty of the municipality is inclusive of the women and the question of promoting the development of women through promoting gender equality. Qoboshiyana (2011) stated that the local government in the Republic of South Africa is based on a concept of decentralisation, which produces three sectors of government, national, provincial, and local, further supported by the local government. According to the Municipal Structures Act 117 of 1998, local government is established in the constitution as a separate domain of government that is interdependent with and tied to national and provincial spheres of government. There is general agreement that local governments are essential to democracy, development, and nation-building in our nation, and that previous policies have left a legacy of egregious inequality and extreme poverty.

To strengthen democracy and advance socioeconomic development, including advancing women's liberation and gender equality, local government has been given a special status and responsibility. As a result, Nzewi and Sikhosana (2020) argued that the participation of women in local government planning and budgeting is attractive to gender equality activists and public administrators because it is a system that provides mechanisms to infuse gender priorities into all the budgetary processes and ensuring that local government budgets are gender aware. Vyas-Doorgapersad (2014) stated that

the matter of gender equality in the local government persists, which is the first point that requires initiatives for women empowerment. The author also made the case that government policies must take gender equality, gender-based tasks, gender-based tasks, and gender-disaggregated data into account.

According to Diedericks and Visagie (2018), in the South African local government context, equal participation is regarded as a cornerstone for the establishment of partnerships between communities and local government administration. Currently, local government service delivery is desperately needed by the people of South Africa. To eliminate historical inequities and provide a higher quality of life for all, municipalities must assure the delivery of desired levels of service to communities.

According to Penceliah (2011), the three domains of government in South Africa have committed to advancing gender equality through various pieces of legislation and policy initiatives, and they have signed on to several international and regional gender instruments. In addition, the author claimed that despite the broad advancements made in the public sector, there are still concerns regarding the slow rate at which women are assuming posts in local government's higher echelons. Women in leadership and senior management would convey a favourable message to women joining the workforce because local government is closest to the people (Selokela, 2012). This is because South Africa is a developing nation, and all branches of the government must take initiative to remedy historical injustices. According to Penceliah (2011), gender mainstreaming should be adopted in South Africa as the recognised global method for advancing gender equality. The phenomenon of gender mainstreaming serves as a method, an approach, and a means of achieving gender equality rather than being an end in and of itself.

Nkosi and Mulaudzi (2017) claim that the South African government was predetermined to develop and implement gender-sensitive policies that encourage and promote the participation of women and ensure equality. Thus, it was anticipated that local governments would actively contribute to the social, economic, and material advancement of their areas, thereby improving the lives of women by offering essential services. Rutaremara (2018) stated that the local government in Rwanda was mandated to include gender equality strategies in their Local Economic Development (LED) policy and programmes. In South African local government, according to Nyiransabimana (2018), gender equality, women empowerment, quotas and the representation of women in political office have become common narratives.

As a result, gender equality is receiving more attention in local government as a fundamental requirement for democratic, inclusive, and successful governance. According to this paradigm, women's involvement might be crucial in providing services to rural communities. Hicks and Buccus (2012) seem to understand the significance of integrating gender into the creation, execution, monitoring, and assessment of their programmes. Few operational plans take gender into account, for example, by describing how the provision of services like electricity, water, and sanitation will be used to meet the needs of women

in particular. This section has already determined that within the international and regional as well as South African public service, gender inequality persists, even though there are policies that should guarantee the implementation of women empowerment and gender equality. Sithole, Todes and Williamson (2012) investigated this issue and made the case that municipal outputs are not gender-specific; some municipalities continue to forgo funding for training programmes in gender analysis, and women are not given access to professional responsibilities. From this, it is clear that the local government is aware of the gender equality and women empowerment policies, but these policies are not implemented. According to Govender and Vyas-Doorgapersad (2013), for municipalities to comply with the laws requiring gender equality, each municipality must conduct a gender-sensitive assessment, identify the best strategies for gender mainstreaming, assess the availability of gender-based training opportunities, examine the framework's implementation, and suggest empowerment strategies to address the issues relating to gender equality.

Meyer (2014) reported that once local government embarks on the implementation of gender mainstreaming initiatives, the senior management should be at the forefront because without the involvement of leadership, nothing can be implemented. According to Govender and Vyas-Doorgapersad (2013), municipalities should assess their gender equality policies and the degree to which they are being implemented in other municipal offices. According to the Commission for Gender Equality (2011), if local governments can persuade political parties to support gender equality and improve the status of women, then this issue will move beyond the scope of their political platforms and become a priority for implementation. The City of Johannesburg (2020) concluded that local government should actively promote gender equality in South Africa regardless of race, gender, class, or other classification of humanity. The City of Johannesburg established that local government is part of the three spheres of government and should implement South Africa's National Policy Framework for Women Empowerment and Gender Equality.

TABLE 1: INSTITUTIONS OF GENDER EQUALITY IN SOUTH AFRICA

LWEGEI	PROGRAMME
CGE	<p>The Commission for Gender Equality (2022) states that CGE is a South African chapter nine constitutional entity to promote and strengthen the inclusion of women as a democratic and constitutional process. The Constitution of South Africa, in creating a framework for a new society, has established a Bill of Rights in Chapter 2 of its first constitution of 1996.</p> <p>As stated above, the main role of CGE is premised on the government of South Africa's desire for a free and equal society in all fundamental and material aspects of life. The institution was established in terms of Section 187 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa to promote respect for gender equality and the protection, development and attainment of gender equality. The core mandate and or business of CGE is to advance promote and protect gender equality in South Africa through undertaking research, public education, policy development, legislative initiatives, effective monitoring and litigation.</p> <p>The Commission's Legal Department had been set up to do the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investigate gender-related complaints. • Evaluate laws, customs, practices and indigenous law, personal and family law affecting gender equality or status of women that are in force or proposed by Parliament. • Recommend to parliament the adoption of laws that will promote gender equality and the status of women. • Monitor compliance with international conventions, covenants and International Charters acceded and ratified by the government that has a bearing on the object of the CGE. • Make Contribution/submission to law making process, especially in laws that affect women adversely and have a bearing on gender equality in South Africa.

<p>DWYPD</p>	<p>The Department of Women, Youth and Persons with Disabilities (2021) states that the department was established and given the mandate to regulate the socio-economic transformation and implementation of the empowerment and participation of women, youth and persons with disabilities. This is done to enable the department to execute strategic leadership, coordination and oversight of government departments and the country in mainstreaming empowerment programmes for women, youth and persons with disabilities.</p> <p>The department has five keys which are administration, social transformation and economic empowerment, policy, stakeholder coordination and knowledge management, youth development and rights of persons with disabilities.</p> <p>Amongst the department's programmes are policy, stakeholder coordination, and knowledge management. The sole purpose of that is to make informed decisions and input with regards to women in South Africa, with a specific reference to all the institutions of government.</p> <p>The department undertakes research, policy analysis, knowledge management, monitoring, evaluation, outreach and stakeholder coordination for women's socio-economic empowerment and gender equality.</p> <p>The Programme consists of the following four sub-programmes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research, Policy Analysis and Knowledge Management: the purpose of the sub-programme is to promote the development of gender-sensitive research, position the department as a hub for content relating to the socioeconomic empowerment of women, and conduct policy analysis to intervene in transformation for women's socio-economic empowerment and gender equality. • Stakeholder Coordination and Outreach: the purpose of the sub-programme is stakeholder management, and to conduct outreach initiatives that promote women's socio-economic empowerment and gender equality. • International Relations: the purpose of the sub-programme is to promote international relations and engagements with women, as well as ensure South Africa's compliance with international treaties on women. • Monitoring and evaluation: the purpose of the sub-programme is to coordinate gender-responsive planning and monitor and evaluate progress on the empowerment of women in line with national development goals as well as regional, continental and international treaties and commitments.
<p>SGJ</p>	<p><u>Sonke</u> is a South African-based non-profit <u>organisation</u> working throughout Africa. We believe women and men, girls and boys can work together to resist patriarchy, advocate for gender justice and achieve gender transformation.</p>
<p>ILM</p>	<p><u>Impendle Local Municipality</u> is a Category B municipality in uMgungundlovu District in KwaZulu-Natal. It is one of seven municipalities in the district. It is outside the primary</p>
	<p>and secondary movement systems of the district, and is some distance away from the major tourist and trade routes, although two important roads mark its borders.</p> <p>The major municipal programme:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>iMpendle Local Municipality</u> conducts an annual Take a Girl Child programme that is treated as an annual event. The annual Take a Girl Child to Work initiative samples 20 <u>matrics</u> students from various <u>iMpendle High Schools</u> with the intention to give them chance to experience a working environment. In this programme, the students participate in on-the-job shadowing with all the municipal departments. The learners are informed of career options available within <u>iMpendle Local Municipality</u>.

Source: Researcher.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The primary goal of this study is to establish the analyse perceptions of women on the mechanism used by public administration to promote equal access in local government, and to recommend effective strategies for public administration to accelerate gender equality in local government. Sahoo, and Goswami, (2024) states that theoretical framework is the lenses that guide the study under research. It is a framework based on an existing theory in a field of inquiry that is related and/or reflects the position of a study, serving as the premise upon which a study is constructed.

FIGURE 1: FEMINIST LIBERAL THEORY

Source: Pasque, (2011)

Liberal Feminist Theory (LFT) emerged in the United States of America (USA) in the early 1960's. It was developed by Betty Friedan. She was the president of National Organization for Women which was founded in 1966.

The central pillar of LFT is to:

- Persuade governments and its institutions to disrupts and abolish laws that were discriminating on the basis of gender. This is through inclusion of women as key stakeholders in promotion of equal access to opportunities in all aspect for women, including but not limited to upward mobility in work places.

In this study LFT is explored to help with the analysis of the perception of women in iMpendle local Municipality where dataset was collected. This framework will furthermore, assist the study with relevant and effective strategies for accelerating gender equality in local government.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted qualitative methodology in which structured interviews were used to collect data from the municipal officials. The adoption of qualitative methodology in this study was guided by its strengths that are premised on the following factors: Qualitative research is based on the lived experiences of the participants. This study is based on the lived experiences within a context of public administration. The researcher had an opportunity to deal with details of all sections of the interview questions, and the research design allowed all participants to freely express themselves in all the questions that were asked during the interviews. Given the stakeholders, the qualitative method was more useful because the issue of women empowerment and gender equality was a complex social issue. Characteristically, the qualitative method uses words rather than numbers to describe the phenomenon to derive meanings through induced hypotheses and case studies. The study investigated the strategies for women empowerment in South African public administration and a qualitative approach was utilised to examine the extent to which the implementation correlates with the lived experiences in public administration. A total of 30 participants were purposively identified and clustered for data collection, and 27 were available for interviews. In terms of data analysis, a mixture of content and thematic analyses were used.

RESULTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Gender Equality As Mechanism For Public Administration To Promote Equal Access In Local Government.

The results are in line with objective number 1, which sought to analyse perceptions of women how Public Administration promote of equal access in Local Government. As such, the study responded to the question, how does public administration promote equal access in local government?

The study makes the following conclusions:

- Women make up the majority of women in public administration, local government, with specific reference to iMpendle Local Municipality, however, there was no evidence that there is equal access to opportunities owing to the majority of men in key and strategic positions in the municipality.
- The Municipality established gender equality structures, yet no effective programs, policies that are implemented as a result of these structures at women disposal, it is a matter that everyone knows they are there, but do not serve what they were established to do.
- iMpendle Local Municipality jurisdictions suffer from the strides of patriarchy. This is based on the fact that the study established that women are not active stakeholders in the formulation of policies, including policies that should benefit them. Where they are involved, the women tend to validate the

patriarchal system that ensures women are content with the periphery while men are at the epicentre of opportunities.

- Women do not understand the power of being a stakeholder in iMpendle Local Municipality. The study observes that being made a stakeholder in the affairs of the municipality is a platform to transform the lives of women. As hinted earlier, the major problem is based on the strides of patriarchy, and it has blinded women in the course of their transformation. As a result, men continue to benefit from the patriarchal system.

- The outlook of opportunities iMpendle Local Municipality continues to put men as the face of Public Administration and local government. Therefore, the key strategies by Public Administration towards accelerating women inclusion remains a challenge because women do not stand up to claim their rightful place towards access to opportunities for gender equality.

- The women are not participating meaningfully towards their empowerment and equality. As a result, iMpendle Local Municipality does not have strategies to ensure that women participation transforms the outlook of the municipality and liberate women toward acceleration of equal opportunities.

POSSIBLE STRATEGIES TO ACCELERATE GENDER EQUALITY IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION AND LOCAL GOVERNMENT

The results are in line with objective number 2, which sought to recommend effective strategies for public administration to accelerate gender equality in local government. As such, the study responded to the question, what are the possible strategies for public administration to accelerate gender equality in local government?

The study made the following conclusions based on this objective:

- All the participants agreed that the municipality should organise and implement programmes for women for capacity development, in terms of municipal programmes and opportunities.

- Women in iMpendle Local Municipal jurisdiction are ready to champion programmes of women's emancipation although they lacked capacity building. As noted in the analysis section, none of the participants understood the existence of gender equality policy, but they do not yield result to accelerate gender equality.

- Women in the jurisdiction of the municipality have not been trained in women empowerment and gender equality. The fact that women have not taken a position that is intentional about what they want to see in these policies says a lot about how they are going to struggle to embrace their opportunities.

- The existence of Public Administration and Local Government does not help women in iMpendle Local Municipality. The women were also happy with nothing happening, because of the social construct that they should follow on

the instructions of men, which affects their opportunities, and acceleration of gender equality.

- Generally, the findings of the study reflected the potential of women inclusion and acceleration of gender equality, if institutional challenges that impede on the acceleration of gender equality.

RECOMMENDATIONS

PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION TO PROMOTE EQUAL ACCESS IN LOCAL GOVERNMENT.

The recommendations are in line with objective number 1, which sought to analyse perceptions of women how Public Administration promote of equal access in Local Government. As such, the study responded to the question, how does public administration promote equal access in local government?

The recommendations are:

- The municipality must conduct intense training and development which is meant to liberate women in the jurisdiction of the iMpendle Local Municipality. This would create an awareness of what it means to be a key stakeholder and or a roleplayer in the formulation of policies with specific reference to WEGEP.

- Other training and development programmes should be for men within the jurisdiction of the municipalities with a specific reference to iMpendle Local Municipality. These would assist in making sure that men are also trained and capacitated to allow women to be part of the policy and law-making that will empower women and enforce gender equality in all parts of the society within the jurisdiction of the municipalities.

- The municipality should establish a relationship with other stakeholders such as businesses, churches, non-profit organisation, and interested parties to deliberate on matters of policy implementation in local government. This would assist the municipality to have a proper consultative process in the municipal jurisdiction. Furthermore, it will govern from an informed position, and give the municipality effective strategies to govern in local government.

- Laws must be premised on women's lived experiences. It is the women who must determine who must do what, in terms of the promotion of women empowerment and gender equality.

- There must be no one size fits all approach to this WEGEP transformation agenda; it should allow the regions to determine how they will implement the WEGEP within their sphere of government.

RECOMMENDATIONS STRATEGIES TO ACCELERATE GENDER EQUALITY

The recommendations are in line with objective number 2, which sought to recommend effective strategies for public administration to accelerate gender equality in local government. As such, the study responded to the question, what are the possible strategies for public administration to accelerate gender equality in local government?

The study made the following recommendations based on this objective:

- Monitoring and evaluation must be determined as reflected in recommendation number one. Policies may follow every phase in a policy formulation process, but if there is no system to examine whether there are any deviations between the set standards and the actual performance, no one will ever be able to effect and or implement any corrective measures.

- Training and development, road shows, and programmes with a specific agenda to create awareness about women empowerment and gender equality, as well as the dangers of not promoting and implementing women empowerment and gender equality.

- The programme of women empowerment and gender equality should also be adopted as a programme of action by political parties. This would assist because government works within political party structures. If political parties adopt women empowerment as their programme of action, the training, implementation, and reporting will be established in the ward committees right up to the national level.

- The Department for Women should be decentralised, and be given a budget from all the structures from national to local spheres of government. This programme should not be stashed in the different departments. There must be a unit for women empowerment and gender equality.

- In the entire entities of government, and the three spheres of government, with a specific reference to iMpendle Local Municipality, patriarchy must be attended to head-on because this system does not only sabotage women, but also it is a conduct and a practice that is against the spirit of the women's constitutional right to equality.

- Local government should recruit men for capacity development for women empowerment and gender equality and in turn, both men and women collaborate to disrupt the culture of patriarchy in society.

- All sectors of society must be allowed to talk about women empowerment and gender equality in different spaces of society. This will create an environment where everyone within the jurisdiction of the municipality is aware of the need to disrupt the culture of patriarchy and include women in the decision-making platforms, with a view to empower women.

- Establishing platforms to discuss implementation strategies of gender equality would give women a voice in their lives and further allow them to suggest solutions on how collectively the society can fight patriarchy which

sabotages the government's effort to include women and relegate any form of discrimination on the bases of gender.

THE VALUE OF THE STUDY

The study showed that there is still a need for a gender balance in public institutions with specific reference to iMpendle Local Municipality. Gender balance is important to shape the perception of women about equal access to opportunities and to accelerate gender equality and abolish laws and policies that impede of accelerating and inclusion of women in gender equality.

- Achieving gender balance in iMpendle Local Municipality would benefit the institution itself, and its members in particular because it would increase its legitimacy. It was clear in the interviews that participants were all for gender balance, and felt this was one of the ways to improve the reputation and image of iMpendle Local Government.

- Gender balance provides benefits for all. As women represent half of the population, they also represent half of the talent, knowledge, skills, creativity and ideas, to mention a few. Thus, not having an equal presence of men and women in iMpendle Local Municipality composition means that the council is ineffectively using all the talent available in society.

- Having an equal presence of women and men can result in better, more representative, opinions and better outcomes of iMpendle Local Municipality activities in general. The men in iMpendle Local Municipality must understand that gender balance is not something against men, but something good for the council and the community in iMpendle Local Municipality jurisdiction. It is more about including women and using all their talents and knowledge and making the most out of that.

- Gender balance is an important part of the public sector and has always been integral and continues to be a priority for the future. A strong emphasis on promoting women empowerment and gender equality has been one of the strands of our local government's success story.

- This is because governments across the world, women are far from local government decision-making, and gender equality thus remains elusive, particularly at the professional level in both the public and private sectors. Lack of women empowerment and gender equality lead to a lack of access to skills and limited opportunities in the labour market. Women and girl empowerment is essential to expand economic growth and promote social development.

CONCLUSION

The study seeks to analyse whether women matter in the South African Public and drawing perceptions from iMpendle Local Municipality. To achieve that, the study analysed perceptions of women on the mechanism used by

public administration to promote equal access in local government, and, recommended effective strategies for public administration to accelerate gender equality in local government. The article began by providing a location of the study, then systematically review gender equality from the perspective of South African Public Administration, and Local Government in general and iMpendle Local Municipality in particular. Following this, a methodology and a conceptual framework was explored to guide the findings and recommendation. Finally, concluded that women are predominantly in the periphery, and remain excluded, and with limited effort on the part of public administration and local government to accelerate gender equality. Then recommended that public administration and local government to disrupts and abolish laws that discriminating on the basis of gender, through introduction of implementation strategies, monitoring and evaluation of policies, and programs to include women and accelerate gender equality.

DISCLOSURE

The study is derived from a PhD study, and the research methodology was adopted to reflect data collection method.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author wishes to thank the Durban University of Technology for making publication funds available.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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